

Lexical Characteristics of Computer Terms in English, Uzbek and Karakalpak Languages

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Abstract: The examination of computer and Internet terms and their comparative comparison between the Uzbek Karakalpak and English languages is one of the real issues; this is thought to be the foundational study in Uzbek linguistics.

Key words: terminology, linguistic phenomenon, terminology, jargon, slang, internet, computer, technology, language, professional.

A challenge facing functional lexicology is the need for lexical recording for certain aspects of linguists' social experiences. Language does not immediately mirror the reality; rather, the world is reflected in the mind, which then stores, encodes, and reinforces it in conventional signals. Many linguistics studies about computer users and the World Wide Web have surfaced in recent years. The emergence of social computer language has been discussed by linguists, who state that "its development is in two directions." First of all, a large number of new terms are emerging to characterize items and happenings on the Internet, therefore producing terminological lexicons utilized by computer experts; secondly, there is a rise in the quantity of users around the world, using specific vocabulary and word-processing tools for online communication. Through his native language." The lexical content of the second communicative aspect of the computer language differs from that of the former and has its own peculiarities. [1:78]

The formation of new industries and the extension of the nomenclature of older sectors will be influenced by the fast growth of science, the media, and high technology. Nonetheless, the extension and modernization of concept names as well as the alteration of nomenclature indicate the evolution of the language's nominative function. The majority of the new units are composed of word processing software. Understanding speech serves as a source of information as well as a guide for formulating rules and schemes. By doing so, we are able to recognize the consequences of the many principles—such as associative processes and analogies—that serve as the foundation for these rules. Lexical units in language. According to M.M. Bakhtin, the activities of people in all areas are related to the use of language, and the Internet is no exception. D.Saidkadirova: "The global computer network stores unlimited information and data. The Internet is a diverse database. It is enough to have access to the data warehouse to use this data. This is what attracts Internet users". The current state of computer and Internet development has activated many processes in the language, first of all, affecting its lexical system, which led to the creation of a special terminological system that represents a diverse professional understanding. [2:45]

Initially, these ideas were limited to specialists, but eventually, PC and Internet users started to understand them. However, they clarify terms using jargon. This explains the jargon used in computers and the Internet nowadays. Linguists' concentration has remained on the fast expanding jargon of computer and Internet users. Computer jargon and the growth of the internet are explained by S.Yu. Tyurina: "Everything went wrong: English terminology and abbreviations—with the introduction of personal computers in the mid-1980s and the start of the popular magazine PC World in 1988. Word-for-word translations into English clogged magazine pages and tainted experts' speeches. The so-called "computer jargon," which has drawn the interest of several

scholars, is based on the updated English terminology. Additionally, it is also noted that technical terms are gradually turning into some emotionally-expressive, often ironic jargons. "[3:67]

The distinctions between word games and seriousness, high-level expression in new words, globalization and virtualization of communication (such as hacking language), computer and Extra linguistic (nonlinguistic) characteristics of Internet jargon, technical capabilities of modern computer networks, qualities of information technologies, and the overall socio-political and sociopsychological context all have a significant impact on certain features of word and word formation on computers and the Internet. A shift in the language used in the region can be attributed to the rise of the Internet. The development of the Internet, according to English linguist David Crystal, is one of the key elements that has caused revolutionary shifts in language. People who are unaware of it frequently find it puzzling when the names are isolated from everything else since they are exclusively for the globe. Because they speak this unique language, those who work with computers feel like they belong to a restricted group. This lexicon contains a large number of offensive terms. As "a kind of public speech characterized by distinctive vocabulary and phraseology, opposed to (often expressively redefined) by the national language," and the particular application of word-means, jargon is described by T.G. Nikitina.

According to Yu.M. Skrebnev, jargon is the colloquial language used by social and professional groups that is interchangeable with comedy in a neutral literary context. Since the names are exclusive to the planet, it might be puzzling to those who are unaware of it when they are removed from everything else. Because they speak this unique language, computer workers have a sense of belonging to a restricted group. This vocabulary has a lot of offensive terms. [4:88] Jargon is described by T.G. Nikitina as "a kind of public speech characterized by distinctive vocabulary and phraseology, opposed to (often expressively redefined) by the national language" in addition to the particular word-means that are specifically used.

In the neutral sphere of literary language, Yu.M. Skrebnev refers to jargon as colloquial terms used by social and professional groups that are interchangeable with word humor. According to him, those who create jargon refer to formal and even neutral language. The relatively open social or professional group conversation known as jargon is distinguished from literary language by the word and expression choices made.

Terms is terminology unique to a given occupation or activity. Computer jargon is the extensive vocabulary of those who have developed a professional interest in computer technology and have made it their way of life (and perhaps their whole existence), such as professional programmers and certain users. The primary purpose of jargon is to convey membership in a somewhat autonomous social group by the use of certain terms, structures, and expressions. Sometimes, the word "jargon" is used to describe twisted, incorrect words spoken. This language is conditional and only makes sense in a certain context, one that contains a lot of artificial and occasionally conditional words and phrases. Nonetheless, there is a propensity for jargon to spread outside of social or professional groups, which contributes significantly to both the democratization and vulgarization of social life and the growing gap between literary and jargon. [5:26]

Jargon, sometimes referred to as social dialect, dialect, is "the type of national language used in verbal communication of a relatively stable social group that unites individuals by their occupation, status, interests and age."

The metaphorization of word meanings in a word game to produce expressive, emotionally charged language is also the linguistic core of jargon.

According to definitions of jargon provided by contemporary scientific linguistics, a jargon is a particular kind of social discourse that differs from the national language with its specific vocabulary and phraseology.

It is described as "the language of any social group that has many and only specific words, including artificial and sometimes conditional words" in the current Russian Dictionary. S. Ojegov and A. Shvedova's "Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language," it's "a group speech, united by any social or other common interest that has many words and expressions that are different from the common language, including artificial and sometimes conditional." It's crucial to remember that, according to the contemporary linguistics definition of jargon, jargon is always used to describe conversation within a specific social group that is brought together by a shared interest in aging. Jargon is a collection of speech characteristics used by individuals who spend time together and share a shared interest. Professional languages are not just the current language form but also lexical systems unique to any given occupation, profession, or production. Professional jargon is distinct from other national language subsystems in that its speakers are also familiar with special language, literary language, and dialect. This is due to its social and communicative position. They seldom utilize common language or local dialects; instead, they employ literary language for non-professional contact, official communication, free professional communication, and professional jargon in professional contexts. The language in its broadest meaning cannot be a professional language. Their linguistic component does not extend to vocabulary and grammatical structure; instead, it is restricted to specialized vocabulary and word construction. Professional speech terms have the property of existing in the same conditions as their analogs, rather than compressing terminological counterparts. [6:34]

CONCLUSION

The study of a professional vocabulary is closely related to acquiring a vocation. In Krisin's words, "some professional expressions serve as symbols of a profession." The distinctiveness of professional jargon, as Krisin has often noted in his writing, is that it is a metaphorical reworking of frequently used words and phrases that conveys meaning. Indeed, one of the most defining characteristics of professional jargon is the use of sophisticated metaphors combined with vivid and persistent phrases.

Jargon is defined in all scientific definitions as speech, not language. Language is a set of symbols (lexical, grammatical, orthographic, etc.) that are specific to a group of people in society. The most crucial aspect of speech action is language, however they are not synonymous. Speech is unique because it is the application of language by particular language users. On the one hand, experts utilize computer terms as a form of professional language when working, but on the other hand, most of the computer users are young people who use computers for their studies, work and interests.

Language groups, phonetics, morphology, semantics, and the use of both professional and general vocabulary, as well as English Karakalpak and Uzbek realities, are all possible with computer and Internet words, which constitute a complex phenomena of language usage. Furthermore noteworthy is the fact that computers and the Internet are a part of a high status social group's subculture. With regard to technical terms, these ideas facilitate communication among professionals in the field, be they programmers or users of computers in general. Their emotional connotations vary, but they are also used interchangeably as synonyms for professional phrases.

REFERENCES

1. Бахтин, М. М. Собрание сочинений: в 7 т. Т. 5. Работы 1940-х – начала 1960-х гг. / ред.: С. Г. Бачаров, Л. А. Гоготишвили ; Ин-т мировой лит. – М., 1997. – С. 159.
2. Бондалетов В.Д. Социальная лингвистика. М.: Просвещение, 1987.-С.71.
3. Заботкина Е.Н. Новая лексика современного английского языка. -Москва, VIII. 1999, - 126 с.

4. Крысин Л.П. Социолингвистические аспекты изучения современного русского языка. М.: Наука, 1989. –С.326.
5. Крысин Л.П. Социолингвистические аспекты изучения современного русского языка. М.: Наука, 1989. –С.69.
6. Лихолитов П.В. Компьютерный жаргон / Русская речь. 1997.- №3.
7. Марочкин А.И. Лексико-фразеологические особенности молодежного жаргона: (На материале речи молодежи г.Воронежа). Дис. на соиск. учен. степ. канд. филол. наук. Воронеж, 1998.
8. Никитина Т.Г. Толковый словарь молодежного сленга: Слова, непонятные взрослым. - М.: Астрель: АСТ, 2003. –С. 4. 736 с Ходакова А.Г. Системная семантика термина (на материале англоязычных терминов интернета). Автореф... кан. филол.наук. –Тула, 2010. -Б. 12.
9. Ожегов С. Шведова Н.Ю.. Толковый словарь русского языка. Москва: Азъ.1992.Саидқодирова Д.С. Инглиз ва ўзбек тиларида интернет терминларининг лингвистик тадқиқи. Филол.фанлари номзоди...дис..-Тошкент, 2017. – С.10.
10. Скребнев Ю.М. Основы стилистики английского языка. М., 2000. – С. 66-72.
11. Скворцов Л. И. Культура языка - достояние социалистической культуры: Кн. Для внеклассного чтения. М.: Просвещение,1980. –С.2